

Research Methodology Teaching and Learning Approaches, Thesis Writing Skills, with Effective Completion of Academic Thesis among Postgraduate Students in Nigerian Universities

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Abstract

Purpose of the Study: *This paper examined the nexus between research methodology teaching and learning approaches, students' thesis writing skills, thesis writing intention, and self-efficacy with effective postgraduate completion of academic thesis in Nigerian Universities.*

Methodology: *Based on a sample of 250 students drawn from Environmental Sciences Faculties at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University in Southeast Nigeria and the University of Lagos in Southwest Nigeria, descriptive and inferential analyses were carried out. Descriptive analytical tools were used to profile teachers' research methodology teaching and the students' research methodology learning styles. In contrast, inferential analyses were employed to test the formulated hypotheses.*

Findings: *This study revealed that research methodology teaching and learning approaches, students' thesis writing skills, students' Perceived Importance of Thesis Writing, Students' Thesis Writing Intention, and Self-efficacy are positively correlated and do have a significant impact on effective postgraduate completion of thesis writing. Consequently, the study recommends a paradigm shift in research methodology teaching in which the distinct skill sets required for writing each of the sections in the various chapters of a thesis are to be inculcated into students in a practical technical writing laboratory environment.*

Recommendations/Conclusion: *This paper fills a gap in knowledge as it draws the attention of research methodology teachers and students to the need to adopt a practical hands-on approach to teaching and learning research methodology. Therefore, the findings of this study could provide useful input for research methodology curriculum development that will adequately equip students with appropriate thesis writing skills for the timely completion of thesis writing in postgraduate programmes.*

Study Type: *Research Paper*

Keywords: Training, Librarians' Training Needs, Information Technology Application, Services Delivery, Public University Libraries

Introduction

Thesis writing is one of the academic requirements for the award of diplomas and degrees in tertiary institutions in various countries across the globe, including Nigeria, with other requirements being continuous assessments and examinations. The tertiary academic institutions in Nigeria consist of Colleges of Education, Polytechnics, and Universities. Final-year students in each of these categories

of tertiary institutions are required to undertake an independent study upon which a report is written and submitted in the form of a term paper, project, thesis, or dissertation. The importance attached to thesis writing in the three classes of tertiary institutions varies. However, in universities, especially at the postgraduate level, which is the focus of this study, that is, M.Sc., MPhil, and PhD, thesis writing is a critical issue, and it is often expected to focus on a specific observed problem or to explore the veracity of some theoretical postulations in reality. Most proposals, and of course, theses/dissertations, despite disciplinary variations, contain an Introduction/Background, Problem Statement, Purpose/Aim/Rationale, Review of Literature, Methodology, Data Presentation and Analysis Discussions, Interpretations, Implications and Conclusions. According to Anyakora and Odimegwu (2022), each of the above-highlighted sections of a thesis requires a uniquely different skill set to work it out correctly. Furthering discussions on thesis writing skills, Anyakora and Odimegwu (2022) submitted that the ability to read and write is undoubtedly necessary for thesis writing. Nevertheless, much more serious efforts need to be made to learn the skills required for effective writing of the various chapters of a thesis. Aitchison and Lee (2006) opined that within research degree programs in universities, thesis writing remains significantly under-theorized, thus manifesting in thesis writing challenges at all levels. Haq and Shahzad (2021) identified a lack of critical thinking and poor writing skills as among the obstacles to effective thesis writing.

Postgraduate (PG) studies offer academic opportunities for specialisation, and their importance in national development cannot be overemphasised, as it is an avenue for uncovering new knowledge. Haq and Shahzad (2021) argued that PG study is expected to generate knowledge by producing graduates with the potential to extend the frontiers of knowledge. Moreover, Kaur and Sindhu (2009) reported that PG degree holders are playing a crucial role in the development of the national economy with increased interest in research work. Research is the bedrock for knowledge production and extension. According to Anyakora and Odimegwu (2022), the paucity of research leads to inevitable stagnation in knowledge production and utilisation, which in turn limits development and human progress. However, research work is a methodological and procedural investigation that ought to be reported in an approved standard form and format. However, this standard form and format could vary from school to school or even across faculties within the same school. Postgraduate students are expected to acquire good research skills for effective thesis writing. The thesis writing effort is considered effective when it meets the approved standard and format, with contents that also meet the expectations of the audience, and is completed within the programme-approved time frame. Therefore, the ability to carry out research and produce a good thesis (research report) is very critical for success in PG studies because PG students are normally assessed by thesis, examination, or both at Master of Science (M.Sc.), specialised Master of Philosophy (MPhil), and Doctor of Philosophy (PhD).

This study analysed the research methodology teaching approach experienced by the student, the research learning approach adopted by the student, the student's approach to thesis writing, the student's perceived importance of thesis writing, the student's thesis writing intention, and self-efficacy, and their influence on effective completion of the academic thesis in Nigerian Universities. Though completion of PG thesis writing could depend on a combination of student and supervisor factors, the student's factors and research teaching method used in teaching the student form the scope of this study. Specifically, the focus is on PG students of the Faculty of Environmental Sciences at the University of Lagos and Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Anambra State.

National Universities Commission Operation in Nigerian Universities

Academic programmes in Nigerian universities are regulated by the National Universities Commission (NUC). The NUC is a federal statutory body that plays the oversight function of supervising and monitoring academic curriculum activities in Nigerian Universities. NUC has a basic duty to ensure the

currency, relevance, and global uniformity of undergraduate academic programmes in universities. Although NUC does not directly supervise postgraduate programmes in a strict sense, the foundational knowledge and skills of graduate students are usually acquired from learning in undergraduate programmes. However, all undergraduate programmes in universities are closely regulated by NUC through the establishment of minimum academic standards (MAS) and accreditation visits to universities.

The National Universities Commission's Minimum Academic Standards (NUCMAS) for programmes in the Faculty of Environmental Sciences, like those of other faculties, are quite elaborate and subsume the syllabus and the expected teaching method for each of the courses. Bakare (2011) explicitly noted that while the NUCMAS sets down the general guidelines of what is to be taught in every programme in the university, the syllabus and method specifically indicate how this is to be done. The syllabus refers to the content or schedule and requirements of each subject. At the same time, the curriculum is the totality of the content to be taught as well as the working objectives of the institution. The syllabus is, therefore, what is to be taught, while the method is how the teaching is to be carried out. The syllabus, method, and curriculum are intimately interwoven, though separate. Method is an important aspect of the trilogy. Generally, a curriculum is necessary as it provides the content and coverage of the subject matter taught in a programme. Therefore, the curriculum makes for uniformity in knowledge content; however, the method of delivery used in knowledge delivery could vary, thus giving rise to variations in the quality of learning outcomes. Hence, this study hypothesised that the research methodology teaching approach used in teaching a student could influence PG thesis completion time.

The theoretical survey of the NUCMAS document provides a rich research methodology curriculum for environmental sciences programs at the undergraduate level. A student who successfully passes through a research methodology course at the undergraduate level and is able to complete the undergraduate thesis would be presumed to possess the right foundation for undertaking an advanced research methodology course at the postgraduate level. It is, therefore, perplexing to observe the inability of many graduate students to graduate on time (GOT) on account of delayed completion of their theses.

Statement of the research problem

It is expected that upon registering for a PG programme, every PG student will aim to graduate on record time. However, the perceived reality in most universities, especially in Nigeria, falls short of this norm as a significant portion of PG students have been found to graduate late and, in some instances, even overstay as a result of some challenges. Furthering academic discussion on PG students graduating on time, Okurame (2008), Ifedili and Omiunu (2012) pointed out that a high proportion of students fail to complete their research works within the time frame, thus leading to late graduation. Olaitan, Ukonze, and Ifeanyiyeze (2009) identified difficulty in selecting an appropriate research topic, lack of knowledge about materials to be used, unfriendly and sometimes aggressive behaviour of supervisors, less motivation from the side of students etc. as challenges to graduating on time (GOT) in PG programmes. The inability of PG students to complete their studies on time has become one of the main concerns of universities globally (Hoon, Narayanan, Sidhu, Choo, Fook, & Muthukrishnan, 2019). Universities pay high attention to GOT because it is one of the criteria used in institutional ranking.

The incidence of late completion or abandoned PG programmes leads to a shortage of specialist manpower required for sustainable national development and growth. Moreover, in the case of public universities (i.e., federal and state-owned) where PG programmes are significantly subsidised, the inability to graduate on time also causes postgraduate programme funding overload without corresponding improved human capital production output. On the part of the student, delayed

programme completion or programme abandonment could affect the student's psyche and lower the student's academic confidence. Moreover, in Nigeria, delayed completion or, in extreme cases, outright abandonment of a PG programme could cause career stagnation for university academic Ph.D. A common practice in Nigerian academia is that promotion of academic staff beyond a certain level is tied to the acquisition of a PhD in addition to other criteria.

The other considerations in the criteria for promotion of academic staff in Nigerian universities include creative output, university teaching experience, participation in university administration, and service to the community. When a student embarks on a PG study, the expected aim at commencement is to graduate on time. In the Nigerian university system, GOT is defined as completing and graduating within eight semesters for a four-year PhD programme. Generally, every PG student desires to graduate within eight semesters. However, many factors could influence the GOT outcome. Jiranek (2010) identified student qualities and personal situations, research facilities and resources, and supervisory and scholarly environment as the key GOT factors. Duze (2013) also submitted that lack of research skills among students, students' laziness, lack of research equipment, supervisor factor, and overloading of staff scholars (staff candidates) are among the factors impeding GOT. Abedi and Benkin (1984) claimed that research work challenges are among the factors that affect the timely completion of postgraduate staff candidates. In view of the observed thesis writing challenges existing in the body of literature among students in tertiary institutions, the efficacy of current research methodology pedagogies in the tertiary education system needs to be examined. A theoretical review of the broader literature on PG students' GOT studies has shown that factors such as research methodology teaching approach, research methodology learning approach, students' thesis writing skills, students' thesis writing intentions, students' self-efficacy, and students' perceived importance of thesis writing have rarely been considered in the existing literature. It is, therefore, essential to evaluate the effect of the above-unexamined factors on GOT in an empirical study such as this.

Objective of the study

The objective of this study is to examine how research methodology teaching, thesis writing skills, perceived importance of research methodology in PG programme intention, and self-efficacy correlate to determine PG students' GOT in Nigerian universities.

Hypothesis

Two sets of null hypotheses were formulated in pursuit of the stated objective as follows:

- **Null Hypothesis (H_{01}):** There are no significant relationships between the respondents' research methodology teaching and studying methods, thesis writing skills, perceived importance of research methodology in PG programme, PG programme intention, and self-efficacy of the respondents, and
- **Testing Null Hypothesis (H_{02}):** There is no significant difference between the proportion of students taught research methodology using the pedagogic approach and those taught by the andragogic method in PG thesis completion time and grades obtained.

Methodology

Research methodology is a way of systematically solving this study's identified problem. The methodology followed for conducting the study includes specifying the research design, sample design, questionnaire design, data collection and statistical tools used for analysing the collected data.

Table 1: Research methodology

Research type	Descriptive and Exploratory Research
Research Approach	Quantitative and Qualitative Approach
Population (Universe) & Sampling Unit	M.Sc. students in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University and University of Lagos (2019-2022)
Sample size	125 PG students
Sampling Area	South-Eastern and South-Western, Nigeria
Sampling Method	Probability sampling – Random sampling
Research Method	Survey
Data type	Primary (Majority of the data) and Secondary Data
Sources/Method of Gathering Primary Data	Questionnaire, Personal Interview and Observation techniques
Sources of Secondary Data	Newspapers, Journals, Magazines, Reports, books, research articles, internet, etc.
Research instrument	Structured Questionnaire
Period of data collection	February 2019 to December 2022
Software used for analysis	SPSS (Version 22.0)

This study is limited to the perceptions of PG students in environmental sciences Faculties in Nigerian universities on how research methodology teaching and learning approaches, students' thesis writing skills, students' perceived importance of thesis writing, students' thesis writing intention, and self-efficacy influence PG students' GOT in Nigerian universities. The scope of data gathering is confined to the Master of Science degree (M.Sc.) within Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Anambra State and University of Lagos, Lagos State, Nigeria. This study is not comparative, but rather, an aggregative approach was adopted in conducting this research in order to suggest some vital improvement measures which could be introduced into research methodology teaching styles in order to improve PG students' thesis writing skills and consequently enhance the GOT rate in Nigerian universities.

Results and Discussion

The data analysis was carried out using an aggregated methodology. After collection, the data were processed and analysed in accordance with the outline laid down for the purpose at the time of developing the research plan. Analysis has been done using various statistical tools to understand the outcomes with reference to the objectives and hypothesis. In order to analyse and provide a proper interpretation of data, various statistical tools (descriptive and inferential) are used. ***Demographic Descriptive Analysis***

(Sample size = 125, Sample size distribution: COOU = 25, UNILAG= 100)

Table 2: Respondents' aggregated demographic profile

Variables	Options	Frequencies	Percentages
Gender	Male	85	68.00
	Female	40	32.00
	Total	125	100
Age	21 -30 years	76	60.80
	31- 40 years	38	30.40
	41- 50 years	09	07.20
	51 and above	02	01.60
	Total	125	100
B.Sc. graduation duration before PG	1-3years	49	39.20
	4 – 6years	69	55.20
	7years and above	07	05.60
	Total	125	100
Post B.Sc. Employment/Occupation type	Professional Practice	79	63.20
	Teaching	09	07.20
	Trading	15	12.00
	Hustling	20	16.00
	None	02	01.60
	Total	125	100

Interpretation and Discussions

Table 2 above shows that 85 respondents, representing 68%, are male while 32% are female. In terms of the respondents' age, the majority (114), representing 91.2 %, belong to the 21 – 40 age group. The demographic analysis gives insight into the characteristics of postgraduate students. The disparity indicated above implies a potential gender imbalance in postgraduate enrolment, all things being equal. The overwhelming 92.2% of students within the age bracket 21-40 years gives the impression that most doctoral students are early-career researchers or academicians seeking advanced education. The results that show the majority (59.2%) are unmarried suggest that many postgraduate students are likely in the early stages of their professional lives. Studies have consistently shown a gender imbalance in postgraduate enrolment, with males outnumbering females. Furthermore, many studies suggest that a significant proportion of doctoral students are unmarried or in long-term relationships. The policy implication of this is that the knowledge of demographic information of postgraduate students can help universities and other policymakers develop strategies to promote diversity, inclusion, and student success.

The results of the descriptive analysis further reveal that 49 of the respondents, representing 39.2%, commenced a postgraduate programme within 3 years after B.Sc. graduation, while another group of 76 of the respondents indicated that they began the PG programme after 4 years and above after completing the undergraduate programme in terms of post-bachelors. Employment/occupation background of the respondents: 79 of the participants, representing 63.2%, were engaged in professional practice within the various fields of environmental sciences (i.e., architecture, building technology, environmental management, estate management, and urban and regional planning). While 35 of the respondents, that is, 28% of the survey participants, were engaged in trading and business activities, it should be noted that general work and trading activities have little or no academic touch and may not enhance a candidate's thesis writing exploits. However, this proposition will be investigated further in this study through cross-tabulation analysis.

Research Methodology Learning and Performance Assessment

(Sample Size = 125, Sample Size Distribution: COOU = 25, UNILAG= 100)

Table 3: Respondents' aggregated research methodology teaching, learning and performance profile

Variables	Options	Frequencies	Percentages
Research Methodology Teaching Method Used by Teachers	Pedagogic (Teacher-Centred – Theoretical Teaching Approach)	108	86.40
	Andragogic (student-centred – Teaching Approach Facilitating Hands-On - Learning)	17	13.60
	Total	125	100
Attractiveness of Research Methodology Learning	Very Attractive	4	03.20
	Attractive	51	40.80
	Unattractive	70	56.00
	Total	125	100
Attractiveness of Thesis Writing to Respondent	Very Attractive	2	01.60
	Attractive	18	14.40
	Unattractive	105	84.00
	Total	125	100
Respondent's Method of Studying	Study research methodology by reading textbooks only (theoretical approach)	41	32.80

Research Methodology	Study research methodology through hands-on practice only	13	10.40
	Study research methodology by reading textbooks and class lecture notes (theoretical approach)	52	41.60
	Study research methodology through hands – on – practice supported by textbooks and notes (Hybrid approach)	19	15.20
	Total	125	100
Respondent's Research Methodology Performance	Solely carried out undergraduate thesis	46	36.80
	Carried out undergraduate thesis largely with external assistance	57	45.60
	Besides my undergraduate thesis, I have carried out at least one research survey	11	08.80
	Besides my undergraduate thesis, I have actively collaborated with others in at least one research survey	7	05.60
	Besides my undergraduate thesis, I have actively collaborated with others in more than one research survey	4	03.20
	Total	125	100

From the above table, it is inferred that 86.4% of the respondents were taught research methodology through the use of teacher – centred- theoretical teaching (pedagogical) approach, while the remaining 13.6% were taught the same course through student-centred – teaching (andragogical) approach, which facilitates hands-on – learning. Therefore, an analysis of the research methodology teaching method used in Nigerian universities reveals that teacher-centred – theoretical teaching is more commonly used than student-centred teaching. The next descriptive analysis was on the ‘attractiveness of research methodology learning’ to the respondents. This variable was investigated on the assumption that students will make extra efforts to study an attractive course. At the same time, the reverse is the case where a course appears unattractive to students. Results of the analysis showed that, on the one hand, the majority of the respondents (56%) consider research methodology learning as an unattractive subject. On the other hand, 40.8 % of the respondents confirmed that research learning is attractive to them. Nevertheless, 3.2% of the respondents see the research methodology learning process as an

attractive course. In the case of the attractiveness of thesis writing, 84% of the respondents are of the opinion that thesis writing is unattractive, while 14.4% say it is attractive. Only a nearly insignificant portion of 1.6% see it as being attractive. This implies that thesis writing is not a pleasant exercise among postgraduate students. The respondent’s method of studying research methodology was the next variable investigated in this survey. Analysis of the information gathered on this variable showed that a whopping 74.4% of the respondents believe that they can pick thesis writing skills through reading textbooks and lecture notes. While those that employ hands-on methods and the use of textbooks to develop thesis writing skills consist of 25.6%. Again, the result of the above analysis indicated the popularity of the theoretical learning approach in research methodology learning over the hands-on practice method. The result also showed that even the hybrid form of using a combination of hands-on and textbooks is not a common practice among the respondents.

The respondents’ research methodology practice performance was examined based on the assumption that practice makes perfect. However, the result revealed first that 36.8 % of the respondents solely executed their undergraduate thesis. In contrast, a larger proportion of the respondents, 45.6%, relied on external assistance to accomplish the writing of their undergraduate thesis. It could be deduced from the finding of the analysis of the ‘research methodology practice performance’ variable that only (36.8%) of the participants who solely carried out their undergraduate thesis had a fair knowledge of research methodology at the undergraduate level. Further inquiry into the respondent’s research methodology practice performance beyond undergraduate thesis writing revealed that less than 9% of the respondents have ever carried out any other research work aside from the undergraduate thesis. In comparison, less than 6% of the participants have ever collaborated with other students in a research study. Moreover, those who have ever collaborated more than once with others in research work are less than 4% of the respondents. The above findings implied that the majority of the respondents had not practised research work and report writing sufficiently to garner the required research experience to support effective thesis writing at the postgraduate level. This confirms the research outcome of (Daniel, 2018; Daniel, Kumar and Omar, 2018), which revealed that graduate students face significant challenges in learning research methods. This is also in agreement with the observations in the earlier research work of Duze (2013), who submitted that lack of research skills among students, students’ laziness, and lack of research equipment, among others, are the factors impeding GOT. Nevertheless, this implication will further be investigated in this study through Cross-tabulation analysis before submitting an academic position on PG students’ research methodology learning and performance profile. The respondents’ thesis writing skills, intention for undertaking PG studies, and perceived importance of research knowledge in GOT.

Thesis Writing Skills, PG Intention, Perceived Importance of Research Knowledge in PG Programme Completion.

(Sample Size = 125, Sample Size Distribution: COOU = 25, UNILAG= 100)

Table 4: Respondents’ aggregated thesis writing skills, PG intention, and importance of research knowledge in PG programme completion.

Variables	Options	Frequencies	Percentages
Respondent’s Thesis Writing Skills	Ability to explicitly write long narratives of seamlessly linked-up ideas	28	22.4
	Ability to think through a phenomenon in new ways	19	15.2

	Ability to read widely in an area, articulating the academic logic, methodology, findings, and conclusion of each of the resource materials read	13	10.4
	Ability to articulate research problem, pointing out the gap in knowledge, what is lost because of the gap, and by who	21	16.8
	Ability to conceptualise the factors influencing a perceived problem and to use the conceptual framework to develop data gathering instrument	9	7.2
	Ability to discuss results of analyses, highlighting the implications of the findings	12	9.6
	Missing Systems	23	18.4
	Total	125	100
Respondent's PG Programme Intention	Undertake PG studies for future career prospect	48	38.4
	Undertake PG studies to upgrade professional practice	24	19.2
	Undertake PG studies to contribute to knowledge	15	12
	Undertake PG studies to upgrade profile for politics	21	16.8
	Undertake PG studies to attain specialty	17	13.6
	Total	125	100
Respondent's Perceived Importance of Research Methodology in PG programme outcome	Very important	20	16
	Important	26	20.8
	Moderately important	31	24.8
	Somewhat important	40	32
	Not important	8	6.4
	Total	125	100
Respondent's Self-efficacy rating	Readily undertook to learn new skills required for thesis writing	16	12.8
	Readily consulted widely for the timely completion of the thesis	21	16.8
	Readily went the extra mile to get and process data for new information	19	15.2

	Readily set the target of starting and finishing the thesis on record time	29	23.2
	Readily plan to work to earn an 'A' grade in my thesis	40	32
	Total	125	100

Interpretation and Discussions

The information contained in Table 4 speaks a lot about the respondents' thesis writing skills, intention for undertaking the PG programme, perceived importance of the knowledge of research methodology in PG programme completion, and their self-efficacy profile. First, the construct termed 'thesis writing skills', which is abstract, was surveyed among the respondents using six measurable variables which were used in this study to define practical thesis writing skills. The variables are abilities to:

- write long, sensible narratives,
- undertake critical thinking of phenomena in innovative ways,
- carry out an evaluative review of existing reports,
- articulate research problem, identify gaps in knowledge,
- conceptualise the factors influencing a perceived problem, develop a conceptual framework for the data-gathering instrument, and
- discuss the results of analyses, highlighting the implications of the findings

Information in the table clearly shows that only 22.4% of the respondents have the capacity to write long, meaningful narratives in a way that seamlessly presents ideas. Again, even a smaller portion of the respondents (15.2%) can think through a phenomenon in new ways. In the areas of articulating academic logic and research problems in a way that identifies gaps in knowledge, a vast majority of the respondents lack these two important capacities needed for effective thesis writing. It is evident from the data in the table that only 10.4% and 16.8% of the respondents, respectively, have such capacities. Yet only 7.2% of the 16.8% could conceptualise the factors influencing the perceived problem in a conceptual framework format that could be used in the development of data-gathering instruments. Furthermore, from the data in the table, only 9.6% of the respondents can effectively discuss the results of the analyses. It is worth noting that the presence and significant size of the missing systems in responses to this section of the questionnaire strongly suggests the uncertainty of some of the respondents as to their thesis writing skills. This result is not in isolation as it is in tandem with the study by Ugwu, Ifeanyieze, and Agbo (2015), which revealed that while postgraduate students knew research writing, they lacked the skills needed to carry it out effectively.

Second, the respondents 'intention to undertake the PG programme was investigated using five variables. The variables are the respondents undertaking PG studies for future career prospects, upgrading professional practice, contributing to knowledge, upgrading their profile for political activities, and attaining a speciality.

A close look at Table 4 reveals that career prospects scored 38.4%, being the highest reason for the pursuit of PG studies among the respondents. This observation agrees with the result of a similar study by Ekpoh (2016) that revealed that better employment prospects had the highest percentage and ranked first as the major reason for students' pursuit of postgraduate studies. The career prospect is followed by the prospect of upgrading professional practice (19.2%), while the prospect of upgrading profile for the pursuit of political ambition comes next (16.8%). It should be noted that the desire to attain a

speciality as well as the desire to contribute to knowledge scored low among the intentions for undertaking PG studies by the respondents, having scored (13.6%), and (12%) respectively. A similar study by Kaur and Sidhu (2009) found that the increasing demand by students for postgraduate education is due to their realisation that postgraduate education enhances their career prospects.

Third, the respondent's perceived importance of research methodology in PG programme completion was assessed on a 5-point Likert scale. The analysis showed, on the one hand, that 36.8% of the respondents perceived research methodology knowledge as being important in completing the PG programme. In contrast, a vast majority (63.2%) did not see the importance of research methodology knowledge in postgraduate GOT. The respondents in this group perceived the need for research methodology knowledge in PG thesis completion as being unimportant, somewhat important, or, at best, moderately important. It isn't very certain to assume that students in this group will rightly prioritise research methodology learning through regular practice and collaborative research work.

Fourth, the term 'self-efficacy', being an abstract construct, was investigated among the respondents by the use of five measurable variables that defined self-efficacy in this study. The variables are willingness to undertake to learn new skills required for thesis writing, consult widely in thesis writing for timely completion of the thesis, go the extra mile to fetch and process data for new information in thesis writing, set the target of starting and finishing thesis writing on record time, and Plan to work in order to earn 'A' grade in thesis writing.

Although the information in Table 4 depicts that a good portion of the respondents (32%) claim to be willing to work towards an 'A' grade in thesis writing assessment, nevertheless, a few of the respondents are willing to engage in those activities that could produce such excellent results. For instance, only 23.2% of the respondents set the target of starting and finishing the thesis in record time. While only about 17% appreciated the need to consult widely among colleagues for the timely completion of the thesis. Yet a little above 15% of the study participants are willing to go the extra mile to obtain and process data that will reveal new information in their study areas. In addition, it was observed that about 13% are willing to learn new skills that may be required for thesis writing. This is consistent with the comments of some postgraduate respondents in the study by Daniel (2021). They said that learning methodology related to research design, data collection and analysis, writing, and concepts in quantitative research methods; *"I struggle to make sense with numbers, more specifically trying to understand what these numbers are telling me. I want to learn and know how to read those numbers."* Respondents who received some form of training in research methods courses reported that research methodology improved the quality of their thesis and helped them gain better grades: "For me, understanding research methodology helped me gain the best grade I could for my dissertation,"

Ranked Respondent's Perceptual Factors Influencing PG Graduating on Time

The respondent's perception of the factors influencing PG graduates on time. The variables were measured on a range of minimum values of 1 to a maximum value of 5. The result of the analysis, as presented in Table 5, shows that thesis writing skills rank 1st with a mean value of 4.51, followed by self-efficacy with a mean value of 4.46 coming second. In the 3rd position is the PG programme intention and research methodology teaching method with a mean value of 4.4. In contrast, the respondents' method of studying research methodology comes 4th with a mean value of 4.12. At the bottom of the ranking is the perceived importance of research methodology in PG programme completion. It was considered necessary to explore possible relationships which may exist among the perceived factors influencing PG GOT.

Table 5: Showing respondents ranked perceptual factors influencing PG GOT

VARIABLES	Minimum	Maximum	MEAN	RANKING
Thesis Writing Skills	1	5	4.51	1 st
Self-efficacy rating	1	5	4.46	2 nd
PG Programme Intention	1	5	4.4	3 rd
Research Methodology Teaching Method Used by Teachers	1	5	4.4	3 rd
Method of Studying Research Methodology	1	5	4.12	4 th
Perceived Importance of Research Methodology in PG programme outcome	1	5	3.82	5 th

Exploring Relationships between the factors influencing PG GOT.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to explore relationships between the six independent variables, namely, research methodology teaching and studying methods, thesis writing skills, perceived importance of research methodology in the PG programme, PG programme intention, and self-efficacy, to achieve the second objective of this study and test the null hypothesis. The analysis's results are shown as correlation values between the behavioural and lifestyle variables in Table 6.

Testing Null Hypothesis (H_0): There are no significant relationships between research methodology teaching and studying methods, thesis writing skills, perceived importance of research methodology in PG programme, PG programme intention, and self-efficacy of the respondents.

Table 6: Correlation matrix of the factors influencing PG GOT

Independent Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Research Methodology Teaching Method used by Teachers	1					
2. Method of Studying Research Methodology	0.61**	1				
3. Thesis Writing Skills	0.665*	0.641**	1			
4. Perceived Importance of Research Methodology in PG programme completion	0.35**	0.29**	0.798**	1		
5. PG Programme Intention	0.378*	0.21**	0.41**	0.30	1	

				0*		
6. Self-efficacy rating	0.1**	0.38**	0.51**	0.29	0.62**	1

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Interpretation and Discussions

Table 6 shows that, on the one hand, all the variables conceived in this study to influence PG's graduating on time correlate positively with one another. In the relationships, a minimum correlation coefficient (r) value of 0.1 exists between the research methodology teaching method and self-efficacy. On the other hand, a maximum correlation coefficient (r) value of 0.798 exists between thesis writing skills and the perceived importance of research methodology in PG programme completion. Moreover, information in the table shows that thesis writing skills significantly strongly correlate positively with the research methodology teaching method used in teaching the respondent and the method of studying research methodology employed by the respondent, at correlation coefficients (r) values of 0.665 and 0.641, respectively. Furthermore, a weak positive correlation exists between respondents' perceived importance of research methodology in PG programme completion, research methodology teaching method used in teaching the respondent, and the technique used in studying research methodology at correlation coefficient (r) values of 0.35 and 0.29, respectively.

Also, PG programme intention positively correlates with the research methodology teaching method used in teaching the respondent ($r = 0.378$), the technique used in studying research ($r = 0.21$), and the perceived importance of research methodology in PG programme completion ($r = 0.3$). Similarly, self-efficacy maintains various strengths of positive correlations with research methodology teaching method used in teaching the respondent ($r = 0.1$), the technique used in studying research ($r = 0.38$), perceived importance of research methodology in PG programme completion ($r = 0.29$), and finally with PG programme intention ($r = 0.62$) all at number of respondents ($n = 125$, $p < .05$). Multicollinearity does not exist as the independent variables are not highly correlated, all 'r' values are > 0.9 .

Decision 1

As the P value is lesser than Sig. Value (0.01) in all the above cases, the Null Hypothesis is rejected. There are varying levels (high, medium, and low) of positive correlations between research methodology teaching and studying methods, thesis writing skills, perceived importance of research methodology in PG programme, PG programme intention, and self-efficacy of the respondents.

Deductions from Correlation Analysis

The results of the correlation analysis showed the degree of strength and direction of the revealed relationships among the PG GOT variables examined in this study. All the variables displayed relatively similar positive correlation patterns between one another, although of varying strengths. Considering the strength of the positive relationships between research methodology teaching method and all other variables, it can be deduced that research teaching methodology can be employed as a basis for creating desired positive changes essentially on research methodology studying method, thesis writing skills.

With good thesis writing skills, prospective PG candidates would likely develop a high self-efficacy profile with the intention of undertaking PG studies that will solve the identified problems, thereby meaningfully contributing to existing knowledge. However, the above propositions are further

examined using cross-tabulation analysis in the succeeding sections of this report to provide more information to address a prior expectation of this study's assumption. An initial expectation anticipates that an andragogic teaching approach will more likely promote PG GOT than the use of a pedagogical approach in teaching research methodology.

Exploring the difference in PG thesis completion time and grade obtained between students taught research methodology using the pedagogic approach and those taught by the andragogic method

Testing Null Hypothesis (H_{02}): There is no significant difference between the proportion of students taught research methodology using the pedagogic approach and those taught by the andragogic method in PG thesis completion time and grades obtained.

Results of Cross-Tabulation Analysis

Responses to the questions:

- (a) "Did you complete your thesis writing within record time?" (No/Yes)
- (b) "Kindly indicate the grade obtained in thesis assessment (i) 'A', (ii) 'B', (iii) 'C', (iv) 'D', (v) 'E', (vi) 'F'" were cross-tabulated against research methodology teaching approach used in teaching the respondent (Pedagogic / Andragogic Approach). The result is shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Result of cross-tabulation of research methodology teaching approach against timely "thesis writing completion and grades obtained by the Respondents.

Research methodology teaching approach	Did you complete your thesis writing within record time?		Total	Grade Obtained						Total
	No	Yes		'A'	'B'	'C'	'D'	'E'	'F'	
Pedagogic Count 99 % within respondents	70 70.7%	29 29.3%	99 100	Nil 0%	1 3.4%	6 20.7%	12 41.4%	6 20.7%	4 13.8%	29 100
Andragogic Count 26	7 26.9%	19 73.1%	26 100	3 11.5%	7 26.9%	10 38.5%	3 11.5%	2 7.7%	1 3.8%	26 100
Total Count % within Respondents	61.6%	38.4%	n = 125	2.4%	6.4%	12.8%	12%	6.4%	4%	

Table 7 shows in the first column that 99 of the respondents were taught research methodology using the pedagogic approach, while 26 were taught using the andragogic approach. The cross-tabulation analysis shows that, on the one hand, 70.7% of the respondents taught by the pedagogic method did not complete their thesis writing on record time, as against 26.9% of those who were taught through the

andragogic method. On the other hand, 73.1% of the respondents taught by the andragogic teaching method completed their thesis writing on record time, as opposed to 29.3% of those who were taught through the pedagogic method. Furthermore, the result of cross-tabulation analysis reveals the performance of the 29 and 19 respondents who completed thesis writing on record time and were taught research methodology using pedagogic and andragogic methods, respectively. It is clear that none of the respondents taught research methodology using pedagogic earned an 'A' grade as against 3 'A's made by those who were by andragogic methods; similarly, higher percentages of those who were taught research methodology using andragogic approach earned 'B's, and 'C's than the group that was taught using the pedagogic method. However, for lower grades of 'D's, 'E's and failure grade 'F's, those who were taught research methodology by pedagogic method had higher percentages in these grade levels than those who were taught using the andragogic approach.

In the cross-tabulation analysis, the Yates' continuity corrected value of 42.321 was associated with a significance level of .000, so the result was held to be significant. Therefore, the finding reveals that a higher portion of the respondents who were taught research methodology using the andragogic method completed their thesis writing than those taught by using the pedagogic method. This implies that the proportion of the respondents who taught research methodology through an andragogic method that completed PG thesis writing on record time is significantly different from the proportion of those who taught the pedagogical process. This is consistent with the observations of Jiranke (2010), who identified student qualities, personal situation, research facilities and resources, and supervisory and scholarly environment as the key GOT factors.

Decision 2

The results in the Table reveal differences in PG thesis writing completion time and grades obtained by the two groups examined in this study. Therefore, the Null Hypothesis is rejected; there are differences in thesis writing completion time and grades obtained by students taught research methodology using a pedagogic approach and those taught by an andragogic method.

Deductions from Cross-Tabulation Analysis

The postgraduate students attended different universities across Nigeria for their undergraduate studies before being admitted into the University of Lagos and Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University for PG programmes. Moreover, a vast majority of these students (99 out of 125) confirmed being taught research methodology through the pedagogical method. This fact suggests the popularity of the pedagogical method among research methodology teachers in various universities in Nigeria.

Findings of the cross-tabulation analysis generally show that students who were taught research methodology through the andragogic method outperformed those who were taught the same course pedagogically. This finding tends to support the assumption that teaching and learning research methodology courses in an andragogic way better equips students with practical thesis writing skills than the pedagogic approach. This outcome affirmed the earlier assertion by Daniel (2022) in his study titled, 'The Role of Research Methodology in Enhancing Postgraduate Students Research Experience' that courses on research methodology are pedagogically monolithic, conceptually challenging, and inflexibly adaptive to individual future career trajectories.

Conclusion

Thesis writing skills are a basic requirement for timely completion of a PG programme, and this skill is learnt from research methodology learning and practice. Thesis writing is a hands-on practical activity, and it ought to be taught and learnt in the same manner. However, research methodology teachers still

teach students pedagogically rather than facilitating the development of relevant skills among the students through an andragogic teaching approach. The results conclude that positive relationships exist between research methodology teaching and learning methods, thesis writing skills, and the importance of research methodology in PG programme completion, PG programme intention, and self-efficacy. This relationship implies that how a student was taught research methodology ultimately determines the student's thesis writing skills.

Recommendation

The following recommendations are hereby made;

1. Research methodology should be taught in postgraduate programmes in universities in a practically oriented manner through an andragogical teaching and learning approach.
2. Postgraduate teachers should regularly attend seminars and programs that enhance their skills and upgrade their knowledge.
3. Postgraduate students need more than a course in research methodology because postgraduate studies, such as a PhD, are essentially research-driven. Consequently, they should undergo courses that address different aspects of research methods.
4. Universities should be ready to provide support services to help students acquire and develop the crucial skills of motivation, self-efficacy, and time management for completing theses.

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